

DIRECTIONS OF DEVELOPMENT OF COMPETITIVENESS OF THE INDUSTRIAL SECTOR OF OIL AND GAS ENGINEERING OF THE REPUBLIC OF AZERBAIJAN

Gargari O.

Student, Azerbaijan State University of Petroleum and Industry
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Abstract

The article considers the directions of development of competitiveness of the industrial sector of oil and gas engineering of the Republic of Azerbaijan. The article indicates that favorable economic measures should be implemented to increase the competitiveness of industrial enterprises. The article also identifies existing problems and identifies ways to solve them. It should be noted that the competitiveness of the oil and gas engineering sector, like other sectors of the economy, is influenced by a number of factors. Therefore, it is important to identify and evaluate the factors influencing the competitiveness of the oil and gas engineering industrial sector of the Republic of Azerbaijan. An important issue is the study of the current situation in the development of the industrial sector and the preparation of appropriate measures.

Keywords: industrial sector, development, investments, national economy, competitiveness

Introduction

The further development of oil and gas engineering in the Republic of Azerbaijan is considered one of the main priorities. The development of the fuel and energy complex at the level of modern requirements is one of the pressing issues in the economic and social life of Azerbaijan. The lack of effective use of equipment from local oil and gas engineering enterprises during oil production in the Republic of Azerbaijan has created serious problems in the development of the industrial sector.

These processes led to the suspension of the activities of some enterprises and changes in the structure of production. When extracting oil, foreign oil companies operating in the Republic of Azerbaijan use products from enterprises that produce oil production equipment belonging to their countries. The use of equipment from foreign companies in oil production has created problems not only for oil engineering enterprises.

Increasing oil and gas production in the Republic of Azerbaijan, accelerating the process of oil transportation and refining leads to an increase in the country's budget revenues, providing employment to the population, and developing other areas of the economy.

Competitiveness in the economic sectors of Azerbaijan can constantly ensure economic development. The corresponding capabilities are formed under the influence of various factors [1].

Main features of the development of the engineering industry of the oil and gas industry.

In general, changes taking place in international sales markets also affect the activities of industrial oil and gas engineering enterprises. Direct factors influencing the activities of industrial oil and gas engineering enterprises are labor resources, consumers and competitors, and indirect factors are the state of the economy in the country, scientific and technical innovations, etc. Environmental factors influencing the activities of industrial enterprises constantly interact. Many of these factors form the micro environment in which industrial enterprises operate. Factors that form the microenvironment can determine the conditions for

the functioning of the economic system in the country [2].

It should be taken into account that there are various factors influencing the competitiveness of the oil and gas engineering complex at the macroeconomic level. These include: the open nature of the economy, the effectiveness of government policy and the financial system, the level of infrastructure development, the mobility of labor markets, etc. The level of natural resource endowment of each country has a serious impact on competitiveness.

First of all, when assessing the influence of factors that shape the competitiveness of manufacturing enterprises, it is necessary to evaluate the possibilities of forming these areas. Building competitiveness in manufacturing sectors in Azerbaijan can also lead to the development of the domestic business environment.

The use of modern innovations is the main condition for increasing the competitiveness of the oil and gas engineering industrial sector of Azerbaijan. Thus, issues of innovation-oriented development of the country and increasing competitiveness are of great importance in the activities of industrial sectors. The main source of formation of competitive advantages of industrial enterprises of the country is the improvement of management and production in industrial spheres, improvement of the quality of raw materials and etc. is considered [3].

Recently, developed countries have improved the methodology for assessing a country's competitiveness. Factors influencing the country's competitiveness from a technological point of view are identified. In addition, the high role of innovative technologies in increasing the country's competitiveness is taken into account. It is in this respect that countries around the world differ in terms of the use of innovative technologies.

Issues of increasing the competitiveness of industries

The development of these areas in each country has a positive effect on its competitiveness. In addition, the presence of effectively functioning institutional institutions in a Azerbaijan is important from the point of

view of the country's competitiveness. Economic institutions are a set of rules that regulate the interaction of

individuals in economic, political, legal and other forms.

Figure 1. Production of machinery and equipment in the structure of industrial production by type of economic activity of the Republic of Azerbaijan (in percent)

Source: [www.stat.gov.az/Azerbaijan industry 2024](http://www.stat.gov.az/Azerbaijan%20industry%202024)

In the structure of industrial production by type of economic activity in the Republic of Azerbaijan in 2010, the share of production of machinery and equipment was 0,6 percent, and in 2015 this figure increased to 0,8 percent. In 2022, this figure dropped to 0,4 percent. The main reason for this was a decrease in the production of machinery and equipment on the domestic market and an increase in import volumes (Table 1).

The development of industrial enterprises in Azerbaijan can lead to a reduction in contract costs, that is, costs associated with the conclusion, registration and protection of property rights. As a result, the activities of small and medium-sized businesses can be organized more efficiently. The effective functioning of financial markets in Azerbaijan, the ease of entry of private banks into the financial market, competition in the banking sector, the development of stock markets, the main features of monetary and exchange rate policy in the Azerbaijan, etc. Factors seriously affect the country's competitiveness. It should be taken into account that the high level and increasing dynamics of savings and investments, low inflation, etc. factors are one of the main conditions that accelerate economic growth in the country [4].

The experience of the world's leading countries shows that the results of economic activity are determined by the level of development achieved by the country, the level of competition in the market, the success of national companies in international markets, and the volume of investments attracted to the country's economy, as well as the level of export growth. For example, if the level of competition between business entities in the Republic of Azerbaijan is higher than in other countries, this leads to an increase in the competitiveness of local companies compared to companies in other countries.

Result

One of the main advantages is the functioning of the country in a free market economy. Thus, countries with closed economies are excluded from existing competition in the world market and have low competitiveness. The fact that the economy is open confirms the competitiveness of the country's economy. In addition, first of all, it is necessary to assess the impact of liberalization of foreign economic relations on economic development. At this time, it is necessary to determine the resistance of local companies to the new competitive environment [5].

In the conditions of a modern market economy, it is necessary to implement long-term strategic measures for the transition to the stage of an innovative economy. The analysis shows that increasing the competitiveness of the oil and gas engineering industry of the Azerbaijan Republic can be carried out based on taking into account mutual economic factors. That is why it is necessary to implement appropriate measures in this area at the state level.

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